

Transforming Young Minds: The Role of Artificial Intelligence in Economic and Financial Education

Holger Arndt

*Department of Subject Didactics, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg,
Erlangen, Germany*

Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg

Prof. Dr. Holger Arndt

Regensburger Straße 160

90478 Nürnberg

Germany

E-Mail: holger.arndt@fau.de

Transforming Young Minds: The Role of Artificial Intelligence in Economic and Financial Education

This paper explores the application of artificial intelligence, specifically focusing on OpenAI's Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT) models 3.5 and 4, in teaching economic and financial principles to elementary school students. The study assesses the GPT models' accuracy, the risk they pose for fostering misconceptions, the consistency of their responses, and their comparative performance. This evaluation involves administering three tests for economic literacy to the ChatGPT models and systematically categorizing their responses based on accuracy. Each response is scrutinized by multiple trained raters. The study finds that GPT-4 outperforms GPT-3.5, answering 98% of the questions correctly and demonstrating superior accuracy and reliability. Furthermore, GPT-4 shows a reduced risk of leading to misconceptions among students. These findings offer significant insights for the integration of AI in primary education.

Keywords: elementary education; financial education; economic education; artificial intelligence, ChatGPT

Introduction

In today's interconnected and complex society, instilling economic and financial literacy from a young age has become increasingly crucial. Children are not merely passive spectators of economic phenomena; they actively participate, making decisions about spending, saving, and even influencing family consumption patterns. However, imparting these concepts at the elementary level often encounters hurdles, including a limited curriculum focus and a lack of teacher expertise in the subject matter.

This article explores the potential of leveraging artificial intelligence (AI), specifically the Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT) models developed by OpenAI, to enhance economic and financial education among young learners. The capabilities of these AI models are examined, with a particular emphasis on ChatGPT versions 3.5 and

4, discussing their ability to deliver personalized learning experiences and accommodate diverse classrooms.

Nevertheless, the incorporation of AI in education is not without its challenges.

Potential issues such as data security, the risk of fostering over-reliance on AI, and the possibility of engendering misconceptions among young learners are considered. The limitations of these AI models and their implications for educational use are also discussed.

To measure the effectiveness of ChatGPT in conveying economic and financial concepts, several research questions are proposed. These questions aim to evaluate the accuracy, consistency, and quality of the responses generated by ChatGPT, as well as the potential for misconceptions to arise from its use. The methodology involves using tests of economic and financial understanding, designed for elementary students, to assess ChatGPT's performance.

The insights obtained from this study contribute to the growing body of literature on AI in education, illuminating both the potential benefits and challenges of integrating AI into elementary education, specifically in the area of economic and financial education. The knowledge garnered from this research can inform educators and policymakers about the potential benefits and drawbacks of using AI as a teaching tool, thus influencing the future of education in the digital age.

Section 1: Grasping the Significance of Economic Education for Young Children

Even at a young age, children frequently encounter economic challenges in their daily lives. They actively participate in the sphere of consumption, influencing family purchasing decisions and becoming targets of corporate marketing strategies. To fulfill their needs, they manage limited resources such as pocket money and time, requiring goods that they partially demand themselves in markets. Children must navigate restrictions in their actions and deal with the risk of making errors. They may also become privy to their parents' financial aspirations and worries, and indirectly grapple with societal issues such as unemployment, inequality, and environmental pollution. They observe characteristics of the local economy and aspects of the working world, as well as the diverse activities of companies (Arndt & Jung, 2013; Batty et al., 2015; Danes, 1994).

To competently navigate these situations and meet the associated demands of perception, evaluation, comprehension, weighing options, decision-making, taking action, and reflection, children require adequate knowledge. They typically gain this knowledge through real-world experiences, forming their own explanations about exchange processes, the availability of money, and economic inequality, even in the absence of formal education (Arndt & Kopp, 2017). However, there is a risk that these everyday conceptions might evolve into misconceptions (Aprea, 2013; Berti & Bombi, 1988; diSessa, 2006; Duit, 1999; Norman, 1983). To prevent this, children require economic education from their early school years.

Despite the importance of economic education, it often receives limited emphasis in the elementary school curriculum. If included at all, economic education is typically

combined with other subjects and usually assigned a low priority. Consequently, economic education plays a minor role in the training of elementary school teachers (Arndt & Jung, 2013; Brophy & Alleman, 2008; Maros & Evans, 2010). This lack of focus may result in teachers feeling uncomfortable with teaching economics, leading to a reluctance to incorporate the subject into their lessons.

While better integration of economic education into curricula and teacher training could address this issue, given that economic education is still not widely implemented at the high-school level (Urban, 2023), this doesn't seem to be a promising short-term solution. An alternative could be the integration of AI-powered tools like ChatGPT into educational scenarios. As the subsequent sections will discuss, these tools have the potential to enhance individualized learning experiences, deal with diverse classrooms, and alleviate some of the challenges associated with teaching economics in elementary schools.

Section 2: Unveiling ChatGPT and Its Potential in Elementary Schools

In recent years, AI technologies have made significant strides in numerous areas (e.g., Kasneci et al., 2023; Mogavi et al., 2023). Particularly promising for educational applications is the AI branch of Natural Language Processing (NLP), which equips computers with the ability to interpret and generate human language. NLP employs algorithms and techniques that enable machines to understand and respond to natural language, facilitating human-computer communication. Large language models, a major

technique in NLP, are trained on extensive data to learn patterns, context, and grammar, thereby generating coherent responses.

ChatGPT, launched by OpenAI in November 2022, employs a large language model called Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT) in its free-to-use version 3.5. Since March 2023, the improved version 4 has been available to paying users. Trained on a much larger text corpus, this version generally provides higher quality answers.

Additionally, the newer version allows for the enhancement of ChatGPT's capabilities via plugins, such as web searching or performing calculations.

ChatGPT's potential lies in its ability to create personalized learning experiences, a feature critically beneficial in the context of teaching economics to elementary students. It provides immediate feedback, allows students to learn at their own pace, and can engage students in interactive learning experiences (Farrokhnia et al., 2023). Given the diversity within classrooms, ChatGPT's ability to tailor responses to individual queries is a valuable asset in managing heterogeneous classes, especially prevalent in elementary schools. ChatGPT aids learners in constructing their economic knowledge and understanding based on their experiences by providing explanations, answering queries, engaging in dialogue, giving examples, and explaining the relevance of a topic. Students can request more or fewer details, ask questions they might hesitate to ask in front of their peers, let ChatGPT test their knowledge, and receive constructive feedback. With ChatGPT's memory function, students can refer back to previous questions and answers, creating a natural and continuous learning experience. This is facilitated through a conversational style with prompts such as:

- "I'm ten years old. Please explain the concept of scarcity in simple words."
- "What do you mean with 'trade-off'?"
- "Explain again, shorter and simpler this time."
- "How is this relevant for my personal life?"
- "Give me a few examples."
- "How is scarcity related to needs?"
- "Summarize the most important points in simple words."
- "Test me."

While ChatGPT is primarily a text-based tool, browser extensions like 'TalkToChatGPT' allow users to interact using spoken language, receiving both spoken and written responses. This feature enables students with limited literacy, particularly prevalent in lower grade levels of elementary schools, to learn with ChatGPT.

In essence, ChatGPT has the potential to serve as a personal tutor for every child by providing individualized learning opportunities.

Section 3: Potential Challenges of Learning with ChatGPT

While ChatGPT offers several promising opportunities for enhancing economic education in elementary schools, its usage also introduces potential challenges that warrant careful consideration.

To start with, there are a few technical limitations, although these are likely to be resolved in the near future. Currently, ChatGPT's input is restricted to text, making it impossible to process images or logical diagrams like mind maps. The same limitation applies to ChatGPT's output, although some visualizations are already possible with the aid of plugins like "Show Me". Furthermore, the basic version of ChatGPT only contains information up until September 2021. However, plugins like "WebPilot" enable it to search the web and thus access current information.

Data security could also be a concern, as some of the users' prompts may be used to further train the model. Another significant challenge is the potential for ChatGPT to facilitate cheating, for example, by completing students' homework. However, this issue reflects more on the need for different homework and assessment tasks rather than on the usefulness of ChatGPT for learning (Adiguzel et al., 2023).

There is also a risk of over-reliance on AI for learning. While AI can enhance learning experiences and offer individualized support, it should not supplant the critical role of teachers or the benefits of human interaction in learning environments. Teachers not only impart knowledge but also provide context, inspire critical thinking, and foster socio-emotional learning (Farrokhinia et al., 2023).

ChatGPT generates new answers for identical prompts, meaning different students may receive varying responses, potentially leading to unequal learning opportunities and fairness issues.

Perhaps most importantly, it's crucial to understand that ChatGPT doesn't truly "understand" the users' prompts or its own responses, even though it may appear to do so. The software derives its "understanding" from a vast amount of text without reflecting on the quality of these texts. As a result, it may reproduce problematic information, leading to biased or discriminatory responses. Moreover, this could result in unhelpful or incorrect answers (Cooper, 2023). For elementary students (and to some extent, their teachers), it may be challenging to discern the correctness of the answers, potentially leading to the assimilation of incorrect information or the development of misconceptions. This risk may be particularly high for complex and abstract economic concepts, where not only is there a higher likelihood of ChatGPT providing incorrect information, but such mistakes may also be harder to detect.

Section 4: Research Questions

The potential challenges associated with ChatGPT underscore the importance of thoughtfully integrating AI tools into educational settings. It is crucial to find a balance that harnesses the benefits of AI while mitigating its potential drawbacks. The central advantage of ChatGPT in the context of elementary economic education lies in its potential for self-regulated and personalized learning, possibly without significant control or intervention by teachers. However, given the limited ability of young children to detect errors, especially in abstract economic concepts, the quality of its answers is paramount. This leads to the following research questions (RQ):

RQ 1: How accurate are the answers provided by ChatGPT when used by elementary school students for learning economic and financial topics?

- *Importance:* This question is vital in assessing the reliability and accuracy of ChatGPT's responses. The correctness of the information provided by ChatGPT is of utmost importance, especially when educating young children. It helps determine whether ChatGPT can be a trusted source of information in supporting economic and financial education for elementary school students.

RQ 2: To what extent do young children acquire misconceptions when learning about economic and financial topics with ChatGPT in elementary schools?

- *Importance:* Understanding the extent to which young children may develop misconceptions is essential for evaluating the effectiveness and appropriateness of ChatGPT as an educational tool. This research question complements RQ 1; obviously, incorrect answers or faulty explanations may lead to misconceptions. However, there may be obviously incorrect answers, e.g., due to a misinterpretation of the question. Since such answers are easily noticed as incorrect, their potential to create misconceptions is limited.

RQ 3: Are the answers provided by ChatGPT consistent when used in the context of economic and financial education for young children?

- *Importance:* Consistency in the responses generated by ChatGPT is crucial for fostering trust and confidence in its educational utility. If the answers vary significantly across different interactions, it raises concerns about the reliability of the information provided. In addition, if different students receive answers of varying quality, this might be considered a fairness issue.

RQ 4: Are there any notable differences in quality between GPT 3.5 and GPT 4 when utilized for teaching economic and financial concepts to elementary school students?

- *Importance:* Understanding the differences in performance between GPT 3.5 and GPT 4 is crucial for assessing potential advancements or improvements in the newer version. Identifying any notable differences can help decide if the paid version is worth the investment.

By addressing these research questions, this study aims to provide valuable insights into the reliability, effectiveness, and suitability of ChatGPT in supporting economic and financial education for elementary school students.

Section 4: Methodology

To investigate the accuracy and consistency of ChatGPT's responses in the context of elementary economic education, ChatGPT was tasked with answering questions derived from tests for economic and financial understanding. Several recent studies have examined ChatGPT's ability to pass standardized tests in various fields such as medicine (Gilson et al., 2023), mathematics (Frieder et al., 2023), physics (West, 2023), law (Choi et al., 2023), and economics (Geerling et al., 2023). These studies primarily focus on how well ChatGPT performs compared to humans, generally yielding positive results. Unlike these studies, this research is less interested in a test score and more concerned with whether its answers are correct (RQ1) or have the potential to create misconceptions (RQ2). Therefore, some questions that can't be answered (e.g., because

they refer to diagrams which ChatGPT can't interpret yet) are omitted, and ChatGPT is asked not only to give the right answer in a multiple-choice question but to explain its choice as well.

Tests of economic and financial understanding, specifically designed for elementary students, were chosen as the main tools for analysis. These tests reflect the expected economic knowledge and competencies that students should have acquired by the end of elementary school. The selection of the tests was based on their suitability for the study's age group and the comprehensiveness of the economic concepts relevant for this age group. In total, three tests were selected:

- **Test 1:** The Financial Fitness for Life - Upper Elementary Test, a widely used standardized test developed by Walstad and Rebeck (2005) for the National Council on Economic Education. It consists of 40 multiple-choice questions covering the topics of spending and credit, earning income, saving, and money management.
- **Test 2:** The second set of questions isn't a typical test but is derived from Educational standards for economic literacy (Retzmann et al., 2010). These questions were selected for the study because they are open-ended questions constructed to measure competence levels of elementary school students. They require rather elaborate answers, making them well-suited to evaluate the quality of ChatGPT's responses. From a total of 25 questions, only 16 were used; the other 9 questions refer to graphical input which couldn't be used by ChatGPT at the time of the data collection. The questions cover topics like consumption, trade and markets, prices, earning, and qualification.
- **Test 3:** The third test is an instrument developed by Arndt and Kopp (2017) to test economic concepts of elementary students. It's a mix of 34 open-ended and multiple-

choice questions covering topics like exchange, money, inflation, prices, markets, consumption, entrepreneurship, and profit.

Each test question was run twice on both evaluated versions of ChatGPT, GPT-3.5 and GPT-4. This allowed for the evaluation of the consistency of responses within each AI version and a comparison of the performance of the two different versions. The repeated runs help in observing if there are significant fluctuations in the quality and correctness of the responses from run to run (RQ 3), while comparing GPT-3.5 and GPT-4 aids in discerning the impact of advancements in the AI model on its performance (RQ 4).

Responses from ChatGPT were systematically classified into four categories in order to holistically analyze its proficiency in tackling open-ended and multiple-choice questions. This classification considered both the correctness of the answer and the quality of its accompanying explanation. The categories are:

1. Correct/Within expectations: This category represents instances where ChatGPT's responses aligned with the anticipated outcomes of the test description.
2. Debatable: In cases where ChatGPT's answers diverged from the test description but were not incorrect per se, they were considered 'debatable'. These occurrences could stem from an alternate interpretation of the question, unanticipated by the test creators. The intent of this study is not primarily to evaluate ChatGPT's test-taking ability, but to ascertain its comprehension of economic concepts and potential for generating misconceptions. Hence, answers falling into this category can still be valid even if they deviate from the test creators' intentions.
3. Obvious misunderstanding: This category includes instances where ChatGPT's responses were glaringly incorrect to the extent that they could easily be identified by

elementary school students, precluding the likelihood of misconceptions. Such scenarios may arise when ChatGPT misconstrues the question in a fundamentally unexpected manner.

4. Incorrect: This category is reserved for instances where ChatGPT provides erroneous answers that could potentially lead to misconceptions.

Two trained raters evaluated ChatGPT's responses. To promote consistency and reliability, the raters completed a training regimen familiarizing them with the rating scale and the criteria defining each category. The training incorporated examples of responses for each category and a guided walkthrough of the rating assignment process. This approach facilitated a comprehensive understanding of the distinctions between categories, enabling the raters to consistently apply the rating scale. In instances of divergent ratings, an independent third rater intervened, and the majority vote decided the final category for further analysis. The inter-rater reliability was ascertained via Cohen's Kappa coefficient, a widely accepted statistical metric in the scientific community that gauges agreement between two raters, adjusting for chance agreement.

Data collection transpired over April, May, and June 2023. It is crucial to note that ChatGPT's response quality could vary or enhance over this period owing to technological advancements.

Details pertaining to each test question and all of ChatGPT's responses can be accessed online (bit.ly/EEAFE_DATA).

Section 5: Results

The outcome of the study is concisely summarized in Table 1, which presents the performance of two evaluated versions of ChatGPT on three different tests. The Cohen's Kappa values, ranging from 0.738 to 1, indicate a substantial to almost perfect interrater reliability. The analysis of ChatGPT's responses to the selected economic and financial understanding tests has revealed several significant findings.

	Test 1		Test 2		Test 3		All tests combined	
	GPT 3.5	GPT 4	GPT 3.5	GPT 4	GPT 3.5	GPT 4	GPT 3.5	GPT 4
Category	3.5	4	3.5	4	GPT 3.5	GPT 4	GPT 3.5	GPT 4
1	37	40	15	15	24	32	76	87
2	0	0	0	0	3	2	3	2
3	2	0	0	0	3	0	5	0
4	1	0	0	0	4	0	5	0
Kappa	0.825	1	1	1	0.741	0.738	0.764	0.746
Significance	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001

Table 1: Categorization of ChatGPT's responses

1. Correctness of Responses (RQ 1):

The initial aspect evaluated was the accuracy of the responses produced by both versions of ChatGPT. On average, GPT-3.5's responses were as expected for 85% of all questions, while 3.4% were debatable. In contrast, 11% of the responses were erroneous. GPT-4 correctly answered 98% of the questions, with 2% deemed debatable and no incorrect answers. This significant difference in accuracy between the two versions indicates GPT-4's superior performance.

2. Risk of Misconceptions (RQ 2):

In terms of potential risks of misconceptions, GPT-3.5's responses presented a 5.6% likelihood. These are two of the few examples:

A) Imagine money wasn't invented! Nobody would have any...

a) If there was no money, we wouldn't be able to get the most important food.

b) If there was no money, people would not work anymore.

****GPT3.5****

a) If there was no money, we would have difficulties obtaining the most important food items. Money helps us buy the things we need.

b) If there was no money, people might not have the same incentive to work since they wouldn't be able to earn wages or income.

In this instance, ChatGPT fails to contemplate the potential use of alternative forms of exchange. Yet, when compared to other responses, this doesn't appear to be a systematic issue. Rather, the given response seems sporadic and unsystematic, in stark contrast to the subsequent example:

B) You want to buy something and want to earn money for it!

You buy lemon and sugar, mix it, dilute it with water and you have lemonade! You build a stand. Glasses and water you get from your parents - your shop is ready!

You paid 20 € for lemons and sugar.

After two hours everything is sold out. You think about the day again. What do you think about the following sentences?

True or false?

I'm satisfied when there is...

a) at least 15 € in my cash register.

...

****GPT3.5-1****

- a) True. Having at least €15 in my cash register would mean I made some profit.

While GPT-3.5 doesn't always err on numerical tasks, its interpretation of numbers appears to be a consistent challenge.

In contrast to GPT-3.5, none of GPT-4's responses showed any risk of misconceptions.

3. Consistency of Responses (RQ 3):

Both GPT-3.5 and GPT-4 exhibited remarkable consistency in their responses during repeated executions of the same test questions. There was no instance where the rating differed across two runs for either version. Differences, when they occurred, were only in the context of provided examples or parts of the explanations, but not the quality of responses. Here is a characteristic example showcasing validly divergent answers where the quality of the rationale was relevant:

The work at your lemonade stand is too much for you! You look for someone who will help you with the work. In return, he gets money from you. How should he be? Write down a characteristic that is most important to you. Why did you decide this way?

****GPT3.5-1**** The most important quality for the person helping me would be *reliability*. I need someone I can trust to be responsible and show up on time for their shifts. This way, I can rely on them to assist with the work and ensure the smooth operation of the lemonade stand.

****GPT3.5-2**** The most important quality for the person helping me would be *friendliness*. It's essential to have someone who can interact well with customers

and create a positive atmosphere at the lemonade stand. A friendly helper can make customers feel welcome and encourage them to purchase lemonade.

4. Comparison Between GPT 3.5 and 4 (RQ 4):

To summarize the comparative analysis of GPT 3.5 and GPT 4: While GPT-3.5 performs commendably, it does occasionally produce incorrect answers, particularly when numbers are involved, a common occurrence in economic and financial education. Conversely, GPT-4's complete lack of erroneous responses suggests it to be a far superior tool, especially for self-regulated learning processes.

Section 6: Discussion

The assessment of ChatGPT's responses to the chosen economic and financial comprehension tests yields several critical implications for AI's application in primary education.

1. Interpretation of the Results:

To begin with, the data indicates a lack of significant fairness issues stemming from varied answer quality, as all responses within the same GPT-version exhibited only minor differences.

Of more significance, the findings infer that both GPT-3.5 and GPT-4 are capable of generating predominantly accurate responses to economic and financial queries appropriate for the primary level. Nonetheless, GPT-3.5's apparent inaccuracies highlight the necessity of vigilant oversight and information validation, given that

young learners might struggle to assess the veracity of such information. Moreover, GPT-3.5 should be cautiously used, if at all, with numerical tasks.

Conversely, GPT-4 demonstrated commendable performance. This study's results suggest that it could be a valuable educational resource for economic and financial instruction and potentially other fields. Moreover, given the quality of its responses, GPT-4 could be employed in informal learning environments, thereby enhancing economic and financial education in scenarios where qualified educators are scarce. Such situations could arise in regions with inadequate educational systems, or due to curricular constraints, or simply when an individual harbors interest in a topic and seeks to further their understanding.

2. Limitations of the Study:

While the results provide valuable insights, it is crucial to acknowledge the study's limitations. Utilizing only three tests might not encompass all the economic and financial concepts pertinent to primary students. The sample size, determined by the number of times each question was run on each version of ChatGPT, is relatively limited, possibly constraining the applicability of the results. Moreover, the quality of ChatGPT's responses seems to fluctuate periodically, with the underlying rationale remaining undisclosed by the software's developers. Nevertheless, considering the rising competition in the AI market and swift technological advancements, it's more plausible for the quality of ChatGPT's answers to improve rather than decline, rendering AI an increasingly promising area for educational purposes and warranting further research.

3. Future Research:

The findings propose that AI tools like ChatGPT can significantly bolster economic education. To leverage AI's opportunities while circumventing potential pitfalls, further research is crucial. Primarily, assessing AI's response quality across diverse areas and difficulty levels is recommended. For instance, while GPT-4 might excel at primary school-level economics, its performance could potentially falter in middle or high school economics. Additionally, determining the competencies students and teachers need to effectively interact with AIs warrants investigation. Furthermore, understanding their values, beliefs, and knowledge regarding AI-assisted learning could facilitate the design of varied strategies to incorporate AIs into the learning process. These strategies should then be developed and evaluated. Particularly for young learners with limited literacy, examining their aptitude in engaging with text-based AIs and how speech-to-text and text-to-speech plugins might support their learning is critical. Future research should also consider exploring other AI models, their potential application in primary education, and the long-term implications of AI usage on learners' comprehension and retention.

This study contributes to the expanding literature on AI in education, underlining both the potential and the challenges of integrating AI into primary education, specifically in the context of economic and financial education.

References

Arndt, H., & Jung, E. (2013). *Ökonomische Bildung in der Primarstufe*. Joachim Herz Stiftung Verlag.

Arndt, H., & Kopp, B. (2017). Economic Concepts of German Primary School Students. In S. Saleh & N. Yakob (Eds.), *Proceedings. Pupils' Diversity and Integration in Education - German and Malaysian Perspectives* (pp. 42-47).

Batty, M., Collins, J. M., & Odders-White, E. (2015). Experimental evidence on the effects of financial education on elementary school students' knowledge, behavior, and attitudes. *Journal of Consumer Affairs*, 49(1), pp. 69-96.

Berti, A. E., & Bombi, A. S. (1988). *The child's construction of economics*. Cambridge University Press.

Brophy, J., & Alleman, J. (2008). Early elementary social studies. In *Handbook of research in social studies education* (pp. 33-49).

Choi, J., Hickman, K., Monahan, A., & Schwarcz, D. (2023). ChatGPT goes to law school. *Minnesota Legal Studies Research Paper No. 23-03*. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4335905>

Danes, S. M. (1994). Parental perceptions of children's financial socialization. *Financial Counseling and Planning*, 5, pp. 127-149.

diSessa, A. A. (2006). A history of Conceptual Change research: threads and fault lines. In K. Sawyer (Ed.), *The Cambridge handbook of the learning sciences* (pp. 265-282). Cambridge.

Duit, R. (1999). Conceptual change approaches in science education. In W. Schnotz, S. Vosniadou, & M. Carretero (Eds.), *New perspectives on conceptual change* (pp. 263-282). New York.

Geerling, W., Mateer, G. D., Wooten, J., & Damodaran, N. (2023). ChatGPT has Aced the Test of Understanding in College Economics: Now What? *The American Economist*, 056943452311696. DOI: 10.1177/05694345231169654

Frieder, S., Pinchetti, L., Griffiths, R.-R., Salvatori, T., Lukasiewicz, T., Petersen, P. C., et al. (2023). *Mathematical Capabilities of ChatGPT*. Retrieved from arXiv: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2301.13867>

Gilson, A., Safranek, C. W., Huang, T., Socrates, V., Chi, L., Taylor, R. A., & Chartash, D. (2023). How does ChatGPT perform on the United States medical licensing examination? The implications of large language models for medical education and knowledge assessment. *JMIR Medical Education*, 9(1), e45312. <https://doi.org/10.2196/45312>

Leswing, K. (2023, March 26). OpenAI announces GPT-4, claims it can beat 90% of humans on the SAT. CNBC. Retrieved from <https://www.cnbc.com/2023/03/14/openai-announces-gpt-4-says-beats-90percent-of-humans-on-sat.html>

Meszaros, B., & Evans

, S. (2010). It's never too early: Why economics education in the elementary classroom. *Social Studies and the Young Learner*, 22(3), pp. 4-7.

Norman, D. A. (1983). Some Observations on Mental Models. In D. Gentner (Ed.), *Mental Models* (pp. 7-14). Hillsdale.

Retzmann, T., Seeber, G., Remmele, B., & Jongebloed, H.-C. (2010). *Ökonomische Bildung an allgemeinbildenden Schulen*. Essen. Retrieved from https://www.wida.wiwi.uni-due.de/fileadmin/fileupload/BWL-WIDA/Publikationen/Retzmann_ua2010_Gutachten.pdf

Urban, C. (2023). *Financial Education in High Schools across America: Trends and Statistics*. Retrieved from <https://papers.carlyurban.com/Report2023.pdf>

Walstad, W., & Rebeck, K. (2005). *Financial Fitness for Life. Upper Elementary Test. Examiner's Manual*. Retrieved from <https://econedlink.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/FFFL-UE-Manual-110404.pdf>

West, C. G. (2023). AI and the FCI: Can ChatGPT project an understanding of introductory physics? arXiv preprint arXiv:2303.01067.